

Universal hip ultrasound screening and preventive treatment in Mongolia: interventions for improvement

Cumulative thesis submitted for the degree of
Ph.D. in Health Sciences at the Faculty of Health Sciences and Medicine,
University of Lucerne

Ulziibat M, Munkhuu B, Schmid R, Baumann T, Essig S. Implementation of a nationwide universal ultrasound screening program for developmental dysplasia of the neonatal hip in Mongolia. *Journal of Children's Orthopaedics*. 2020; 14(4):273-280.
<https://doi.org/10.1302/1863-2548.14.200029>

Ulziibat M, Munkhuu B, Bataa A, Schmid R, Baumann T, Essig S. Traditional Mongolian swaddling and developmental dysplasia of the hip: a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Pediatrics*. 2021; 21:450. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-021-02910-x>

Ulziibat M, Munkhuu B, Schmid R, Wyder C, Baumann T, Essig S. Comparison of quality and interpretation of newborn ultrasound screening examinations for developmental dysplasia of the hip by basically trained nurses and junior physicians with no previous ultrasound experience. *PLoS ONE*. 2024; 19(4): e0300753. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0300753>

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18-454-355
Lucerne, 2024

Submitted on: 24th April 2024

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DOI: DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10814181

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Acknowledgements

I would like to express my thanks to the Swiss-Mongolian Pediatric Project (SMOPP) team, Dr. med. Thomas Baumann, Dr. med Bayalag Munkhuu, Dr. med. Raoul Schmid, Dr. med. Stefan Essig, Dr. med. Corinne Wyder, Dr. med. Petrign Toendury and Dr. med. Reto Gambon under whose support I have started this study and chose this topic and began the thesis, and whose thoughtful advice often served to give me a sense of direction during my studies. The studies received financial support from the SMOPP.

I would like to thank my supervisor, Prof. Dr. Armin Gemperli, for his valuable support in methodological and statistical questions, insightful discussions, supervision, and help in carrying out this project.

I am very grateful to my supervisor Prof. Dr. med Thomas Dreher, for providing helpful suggestions resulting in substantial improvements of this thesis.

I sincerely thank Dr. med, et phil. Stefan Essig and my colleague Prof. Dr. med Bayalag Munkhuu for their continuous support, valuable guidance, constructive discussions, professional inputs, and encouragement throughout my doctorate. This project would not have been possible without their positive outlook and confidence in my research.

My gratitude goes to all the co-authors for their valuable contributions to the published papers.

And finally, I would like to thank my family, parents and friends for supporting and encouraging me in the last years throughout this Ph.D. project and my life in general. They kept me going on, and this thesis would not have been possible without their support.

Summary

Developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH) is a significant health problem that can lead to lifelong treated or disabled individuals if the diagnosis is missed in the first weeks of life. In Mongolia, an ultrasonic method (Graf) of DDH screening was introduced, piloted, and expanded as a nationwide newborn screening program in 2010. Trained neonatologists or pediatricians perform the hip ultrasound screening following standardized procedures and are responsible for the flexion-abduction treatment, if necessary. Complete documentation of all cases is mandatory. Screening, follow-up monitoring, and flexion-abduction treatment are offered free of charge. The program aims to screen every newborn baby using hip ultrasound and provide early preventive treatment to eliminate disability due to DDH. As Mongolia is the first Asian country to launch a program of universal ultrasound screening for DDH, we needed to determine its coverage and treatment rate. During the implementation of the screening, we documented that physiological immaturity (Graf's Type 2a) hips degrade and develop DDH. In these cases, unfavorable mechanical conditions may exist after birth since traditional Mongolian swaddling requires a tight wrapping with stretched legs, and the hips are held in an adducted position. Therefore, traditional swaddling possibly increases the risk for DDH. This hypothesis was tested with a randomized controlled trial. Another challenge of the nationwide screening program was a human resources issue. Because resources are limited, adequately trained physicians are not always available, especially in remote rural areas. Thus we compared the quality and interpretation of hip ultrasound between trained nurses and junior physicians with no previous ultrasound experiences. This thesis demonstrated that a simplified diagnostic and therapeutic framework for hip ultrasound DDH screening for newborns was successfully deployed in Mongolia, providing high surveillance coverage and appropriate treatment. This Mongolian experience may support further international discussion on universal ultrasound screening using the Graf method for DDH. Furthermore, the thesis provides evidence that traditional Mongolian swaddling where legs are extended, and hips are in extension and adduction position increases the risk for DDH; nurses can obtain standard hip sonograms according to the

Graf method with equal quality as junior physicians after receiving standard training. These results allow us to improve the coverage and quality of the nationwide screening program in Mongolia.

List of abbreviations

DDH	Developmental Dysplasia of the Hip
NCMCH	National Center for Maternal and Child Health
MOH	Ministry of Health
SMOPP	Swiss - Mongolian Pediatric Project

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1. Background

Developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH) is one of the significant health problems that can lead to lifelong disability if the diagnosis is missed in the first weeks of life [1, 2]. According to a study [3], 48.4% were found to have underlying hip dysplasia as the etiology of total hip arthroplasty for osteoarthritis in patients under 50 years old. Severity can range from minor acetabular dysplasia to complete dislocation. Severe dysplasia frequently results in a dislocation of the femoral head already in childhood, while mild forms cause pain and signs of wear and tear in adulthood. Estimates of the incidence of DDH are quite variable and depend on detection methods, the ages of the child, and diagnostic criteria [4, 5]. Mongolian studies reported a 1.2 to 1.3% incidence of DDH (Type 2c, D, 3, and 4) by the Graf method of ultrasound, which is comparable to that in European neonates (1–2%) [6, 7].

Early diagnosis of DDH is the most crucial obligation for achieving the best outcome, using a simple, non-surgical method in the shortest possible time [8-11]. Delayed diagnosis results in losing the potential to remodel the acetabular roof, lengthening the treatment duration, and may cause complications such as osteochondrosis, etc [1, 2, 12]. According to Graf [13], the ultrasound classification provides basic information about the biomechanical situation and is widely used in many countries. The treatment is usually based on the degree of severity of DDH. The maturation of DDH through suitable, preventive treatment measures in the first 12 weeks of life leads to complete maturation of the hip joints [13, 14]. Treatment beyond this point is typically prolonged, often resulting in an orthopedic repair with a poorer prognosis [15-18]. The overall costs for orthopedic DDH treatment, hospitalizations, surgery, and rehabilitation are much higher than its prevention based on early detection by ultrasound with the Graf technique [19-21].

The introduction of the Graf method of hip ultrasonography and more effective non-surgical treatment in Mongolia since 2010 changed the policy and time of diagnosis in children with DDH, resulting in more prevented cases of childhood disabilities. In 2011, a prospective birth cohort study [6] of 8356 newborns revealed that hip ultrasound is feasible in the tertiary pediatric hospital of Ulaanbaatar (National Center for Maternal and

Child Health; NCMCH) that the incidence of DDH in neonates is comparable with that in European neonates (1% to 2%) and that early ultrasound-based assessment and flexion-abduction treatment of DDH leads to maturation of the hip joints in all cases. Based on the study results and NCMCH being a key player in national policy and program drafting in maternal and child health, the Mongolian Ministry of Health (MOH) decided to initiate ultrasound for DDH in newborns throughout Ulaanbaatar. In 2017, the Mongolian Government approved a nationwide screening program that required all maternity hospitals to offer ultrasound hip screening by Graf technique for all newborns. Trained neonatologists or pediatricians perform the hip ultrasound screening following standardized procedures and are responsible for the flexion-abduction treatment, if necessary. Complete documentation of all cases is mandatory. Screening, follow-up monitoring, and flexion-abduction treatment are offered free of charge [22]. The program aims to screen every newborn baby using hip ultrasound and provide early preventive treatment to eliminate disability due to DDH.

Rural Mongolians are a population group that experiences significant health disparities due to some unique features, such as a dispersed population over a vast territory and under a nomadic lifestyle. Since 2015, the screening has been expanded to provincial (aimag) hospitals and major sub-provincial (soum) hospitals as a primary source of medical care for nomadic rural residents. However, hospitals face many significant and unique barriers when considering the widespread adoption of newer innovations in health care, such as hip ultrasound screening in newborns. One barrier is a lack of trained physicians capable of performing hip ultrasounds (huge turnover within the doctor's teams, drainage of knowledge and ability, etc.) like in other developing countries [23]. Because resources are limited, physicians are not always available around-the-clock or on remote emergency calls from rural areas. The hip ultrasound screening has not been widely implemented at the sub-provincial (soum) hospitals in a resource-poor setting to critically look at operational issues that might affect its implementation on a larger scale and its ability to reduce hip dislocation incidence at an epidemiological level. In Mongolia, early DDH detection is essential in rural areas because swaddling has a long tradition

and is a well-known risk factor for the aggravation of DDH [24-27]. In these cases, unfavorable mechanical conditions may exist after birth since traditional Mongolian swaddling requires a tight wrapping with stretched legs, and the hips are held in an adducted position. Therefore, this thesis aims to review the current situation of the newborn ultrasound screening program for DDH in Mongolia and provide evidence for addressing the program's challenges.

1.2. The rationale of the thesis

The overarching goal of this thesis was to evaluate the Mongolian screening to inform the future improvement of DDH screening in Mongolia. Specific aims were:

1. to determine the coverage and treatment rate of the nationwide screening program in Mongolia - Study 1.
2. to test the hypothesis that traditional Mongolian swaddling of infants, where arms and legs are stretched with a tight wrapping and hips are in extension and adduction position, may lead to abnormal maturation and formation of the hip joint; and is a contributing factor for developmental dysplasia of the hip (DDH) - Study 2.
3. to compare the quality and interpretation of hip ultrasound screening examinations by basically trained nurses to junior-physicians with no previous ultrasound experience - Study 3.

The work presented in this thesis was conducted within the Swiss Mongolian Pediatric Project (SMOPP) research group, a humanitarian aid project (www.smopp.ch).

1.3. Methodology

Successful implementation of universal newborn hip ultrasound screening should be the goal to eliminate disability due to DDH in the country. However, challenges in doing so in developing, resource-limited countries still exist. The studies were designed to address the challenges of the national screening program. A mixed methods approach was adopted because it could contextualize the topic of DDH ultrasound screening. Figure 1

illustrates how the thesis studies are related to the National Screening Program and its challenges.

The first descriptive study (the Coverage study) used data from birth statistics and hip ultrasound screening during 2010-2019 from 29 hospitals retrospectively reviewed (2010 to 2016, pre-nationwide phase; and 2017 to 2019, nationwide program). Since data were collected at multicentre sites, screeners used a web-based platform to upload images for quality surveillance.

The second study (the Swaddling study) of 80 newborns with one or two hips at risk of worsening to developmental dysplasia of the hip (Graf Type 2a; physiologically immature hips) were randomized into 2 groups at a tertiary hospital in Ulaanbaatar. The “swaddling” group (n=40) was swaddled in the typical traditional Mongolian method for a month, while the “non-swaddling” group (n=40) was instructed not to swaddle at all. All enrollees were followed up monthly by hip ultrasound and treated with an abduction-flexion splint if necessary. The groups were compared on the rate of Graf’s “non-Type 1” hips at follow-up controls as the primary outcome.

In the third study (the Nurses vs. junior physicians study), 6 nurses and 6 junior physician volunteers with no previous ultrasound experience from 3 hospitals were trained to produce Graf’s standard plane sonograms of the hip and to identify “non-Type A” hips. 201 newborns were examined daily before discharge from the hospital according to the national guideline. Two standard documentation images of each hip were saved digitally using the HipScreen system, a web-based quality control system. The quality of the newborn hip ultrasound images was measured by 4 indicators (anatomical identification, standard plane, three measurement lines, transducer tilting) and the interpretation of “Group A” (Graf’s Type 1 hip) or “Non- Group A” (Graf’s non-Type 1 hip) hips. The groups were compared on the proportion of the quality of sonograms and the correct interpretation. Two supervisors’ final agreed diagnosis, according to Graf, was considered the final reference for the study purposes.

Figure 1. Connection of Ph.D. thesis and the Mongolia National Screening Program challenges

Chapter 2: Implementation of a nationwide universal ultrasound screening program for developmental dysplasia of the neonatal hip in Mongolia

Ulziibat M, Munkhuu B, Schmid R, Baumann T, Essig S

Published in Journal of Children's Orthopaedics. 2020; 14(4):273-280.

<https://doi.org/10.1302/1863-2548.14>

Chapter 3: Traditional Mongolian swaddling and developmental dysplasia of the hip: a randomized controlled trial

Ulziibat M, Munkhuu B, Bataa A, Schmid R, Baumann T, Essig S.

Published in BMC Pediatrics. 2021; 21:450.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-021-02910-x>

Chapter 4: Comparison of quality and interpretation of newborn ultrasound screening examinations for developmental dysplasia of the hip by basically trained nurses and junior physicians with no previous ultrasound experience

Ulziibat M, Munkhuu B, Schmid R, Wyder C, Baumann T, Essig S.

Published in PLoS ONE. 2024; 19(4): e0300753.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0300753>

Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1 Summary of main results

The thesis is the first to determine the coverage and treatment rate of the universal ultrasound screening for newborns with DDH in Mongolia. With the hip ultrasound screening coverage rate of 82.1% in 2019, the first study demonstrated that the nationwide ultrasound screening of DDH allowed a relatively high coverage rate even in otherwise low-resource rural areas in Mongolia. The universal DDH screening detected severely dysplastic to dislocated hips at a rate of 1.2% of all newborns by the “ABCD” system, a modified Graf method of hip ultrasound. The children with dysplastic hips were treated with conservative treatment, e.g., a flexion-abduction orthosis.

The second study provides evidence that traditional swaddling contributes significantly to delayed maturation of the physiologically immature Type 2a hips and the development of DDH. All children were finally discharged with healthy Type A hips but swaddling significantly prolonged time to Type A hips. Furthermore, “non-Type A” hips correlated with swaddling length per day and frequency in days.

The third study checked whether nurses could be practical alternatives where suitable hip ultrasound-trained doctors are unavailable in remote areas. The study revealed no statistically significant difference in the quality of Graf’s standard plane images between the providers: junior physicians and nurses (80.6% and 77.3%; $p=0.553$). Eventually, 97.2% (105) of the junior group and 94.6% (104) of the nurse group correctly diagnosed the “Group A” (Graf’s Type 1 hip) or “Non- Group A” ($p=0.321$). The common error among the groups was missing the lower limb.

5.2. Discussion and interpretation of results

Implementation of a nationwide universal ultrasound screening program for developmental dysplasia of the neonatal hip in Mongolia

The thesis results reveal that the hip ultrasound screening coverage rate in newborns has increased and reached over 80% even though the screening was comparatively new to

the general population and healthcare professionals. There might be some explanations for how the new ultrasound screening method has been successfully used in Mongolia.

The first explanation is the introduction of Graf's method of hip ultrasound to Mongolia. The Swiss Mongolian Pediatric Project (SMOPP), a humanitarian aid project, introduced the method in 2007. In 2010, a prospective birth cohort study [1] of 8356 newborns revealed that hip ultrasound is feasible and the incidence of DDH in neonates is comparable with that in European neonates (1% to 2%) and early ultrasound-based assessment and flexion-abduction treatment of DDH leads to maturation of the hip joints in all cases. Based on the study results, the Mongolian MOH and the Mongolian Government approved a nationwide screening program that required all maternity hospitals to offer ultrasound hip screening by Graf technique for all newborns.

Secondly, the health system of Mongolia has to be considered. In Mongolia, initiating a universal screening program was justifiable since almost all births occur in just a few centralized maternity hospitals [2], and most newborns are provided with a general checkup by neonatologists or pediatricians within the first two days of life before most families leave the hospital and return to the vast countryside. These exams offer an opportunity for a routine check of hips by ultrasound and the earliest possible start for preventive flexion-abduction treatment if indicated. Furthermore, statistical reports describe severe concerns within the country in relation to DDH [3]. There were no reliable examination and treatment methods in place, and significant variations in diagnosis of DDH were common prior to the advent of the standardized screening program, leading to confusion for medical professionals and parents.

The third explanation is the equipment and training of neonatologists and pediatricians. Hip ultrasound screening was introduced stepwise until all 29 governmental hospitals across the country were equipped with necessary ultrasound machines, transducers, and cradles by SMOPP. Since neonatologists or pediatricians provide a general checkup for every newborn within the first two days of life, the SMOPP team trained all neonatologists or pediatricians. They perform the hip ultrasound screening

following standardized procedures and are responsible for the flexion-abduction treatment, if necessary. The neonatologists or pediatricians offer free-of-charge screening, follow-up monitoring, and flexion-abduction treatment. Every year, a refresher course is mandatory for every screener.

Moreover, the fourth explanation is the “ABCD system”. In Mongolia, the original 12 Graf subtypes have been replaced by a more straightforward and more practical system, the “ABCD system” [4]. It classifies the bony and cartilaginous roof as correlated to age, comparing spontaneous maturation during the first weeks of life to Graf’s average 1° alpha per week [5]. All children diagnosed with DDH in Mongolia are now treated with a Tübingen orthosis.

Lastly, the quality control system should not be forgotten. Although the simplified “ABCD system” allowed narrowing treatment strategies in the first days of life and helped compensate for the massive turnover of screeners in governmental maternal hospitals in Mongolia, the method is only as good as its users. When the Graf technique was used correctly, the rates of open reductions, acetabuloplasty, and head necrosis were reduced [6]. To achieve such results, the quality of knowledge and skills of screens is crucial; under- or over-diagnosis would lead to costly and unnecessary treatment or handicaps. One of the leading causes of misdiagnosis in infant hip sonography is errors due to poor-quality hip ultrasounds [7]. Errors come from poor technique, tilting of transducers, and subsequent measurement bias that leads to the wrong diagnosis and, ultimately, incorrect procedures that cause unnecessary harm for babies. Such errors may be more likely to occur without a quality control system. Therefore, a quality control system should allow reliable review of diagnosis and treatment of DDH and continuous education of screening doctors. This Mongolian example shows that an internet-based quality platform can have good acceptance and support screeners, even in developing countries where knowledge and experience may be lacking.

Traditional Mongolian swaddling and developmental dysplasia of the hip

Although, to our knowledge, no previous RCT tested the effect of swaddling on physiologically immature hips, our study results are supported by findings from several observational studies in different countries where swaddling was a long-standing tradition [8-10]. There might be some explanations for how swaddling has significantly contributed to the increased rates of “non-Type 1” hips and DDH in the current study.

First, the anatomical development of the hip joint. Several studies suggest that baby hips may be well-formed before birth and become more dysplastic around birth due to postnatal influences on DDH [11, 12]. In addition, some studies suggested that transient ligamentous laxity from maternal relaxin and abnormal mechanical pressures after birth may contribute to soft tissue deformation in the mature infant.

Second, the initial hip type (Graf Type 2a). Although these hips have considerable potential for spontaneous maturation, they are physiologically immature, located between perfect hips and DDH, and at risk of worsening. The rate of spontaneous normalization in type 2a hips is reported to be 90–97%, whereas dysplasia persists or worsens in 3–10% of cases [13, 14]. Two studies evaluated predictors of worsening sonographic findings; an alpha angle < 55 on the initial ultrasonography, instability, central nervous system anomalies, and unilateral Type 2a hips were independent predictors of sonographic worsening [15, 16].

Third, the swaddling method. Not all swaddling techniques pose similar risks to the hips. The harmful effect of swaddling on DDH may be seen in cultures that swaddle with hips adducted and extended. Several studies indicate that extension of the normal infants' hip flexion contracture may contribute to DDH, including dislocation [17, 18]. Also, in a rat model, straight-leg swaddling has been shown to have harmful effects on an infant's hips, especially in those who have been swaddled at a younger age and those who have undergone prolonged swaddling [19].

Fourth, the swaddling timing and duration might indeed be another crucial issue. Some epidemiological studies indicate that swaddling is a contributing factor but do not present

detailed data concerning the initiation time, duration, and frequency of swaddling. Swaddling is commonly used in the first 3–5 months of children’s life, which is the time of significant potential for maturation time of young infants’ hip joints. This overlapping time of swaddling and maturation is potentially critical, especially for physiologically immature hips.

Comparison of nurse-performed hip ultrasound in newborns

In developing countries implementing and sustaining any newborn screening, including newborn hip ultrasound, is challenging due to potential political instability, lack of trained human resources, less developed public health systems, etc. [20]. The hip ultrasound screening implementation has not been smooth, especially in foremost provincial and sub-provincial hospitals physicians are not always available when they are on emergency calls from remote rural areas. The need for a possible alternative approach to screen every newborn baby for DDH by ultrasound is obvious when trained doctors are not available, especially in rural areas. To address the challenge of detecting “non-Type A” (Graf’s non-Type 1 hip) cases before discharge from maternity hospital (usually, after birth, newborns stay 1-2 days), it might be wise to train nurses since nurses are a more stable group in terms of mobility or changing workplace in the country. This is especially crucial in rural hospitals where nomadic rural residents receive maternity and health services.

Although the role of nurse-led hip ultrasonography is insufficiently studied, Professor Graf, the founder of the hip ultrasound method, repeatedly mentions that the nurse-performed hip ultrasound has good accuracy. A study aimed to evaluate healthcare workers’ ability to classify ultrasound images into a Graf system [21]. The screening team consisted of 3 physicians and 4 nurses at the infant health care system, with no previous ultrasound experience in the Netherlands. After theoretical and practical training, seven nurses and physicians of the participating infant health centers reported their findings on hip sonograms of 80 children. This was repeated five months later. From the two evaluation moments, the intra-observer agreement and the inter-observer agreement were

determined. Based on the study results, the authors concluded that the inter- and intra-observer agreement is comparable to similar studies in which the participants had a professional background in ultrasound examination. The level of agreement of the trainees in the perspective of the screening process was considered sufficient [21]. However, this study addressed only the intra- and inter-observer variability in reading a sonogram. Therefore, the findings of this study and our results cannot be compared.

On the other hand, nurses are key players in the newborn screening program, and their role is crucial in increasing newborn screening coverage. Considered front liners, nurses are usually the first contact with parents in a primary care setting or health facility, allowing them to advocate and educate parents on newborn screening. Besides these advantages recently, several studies have shown that appropriately trained nurses can perform some ultrasound scans [22-27].

5.3. Implications

The findings from this thesis provide insights into the nationwide ultrasound screening for newborns with DDH in Mongolia, such as its surveillance coverage, dysplastic hip incidences, and treatment. The knowledge gained from this thesis led to the “Mongolian national guideline for the neonatal hip ultrasound screening” updating with the “ABCD system,” which was approved by the MOH in 2021. This is currently being implemented, with a milestone being reached in 2030.

The studies of this thesis have not only supplemented existing knowledge but also have proved that a new simplified and modified Graf’s system of diagnostic and treatment procedure with quality control is successful, tight swaddling where arms and legs are extended and hips are in extension and adduction position increases the risk for DDH and early diagnosis of DDH. Furthermore, the thesis showed that nurses could be a practical alternative where suitable hip ultrasound-trained doctors are unavailable in remote areas. Mainly, these findings are significant because the screening project has been expanded to sub-provincial hospitals as a primary source of medical care for nomadic rural residents.

All the thesis findings incited and gave impulses to the dynamic international discussions on DDH and its early diagnosis and treatment.

Future perspectives: Considering the criteria of successful newborn screening programs ($\geq 95\%$ of all newborns must be screened) [65], the Mongolia newborn hip ultrasound screening program is still in its infancy. The goal of the Mongolian nationwide hip ultrasound screening program is to screen every newborn baby using hip ultrasound and to provide early preventive treatment to eliminate childhood disabilities due to DDH. Therefore, like any other nationwide screening program, four inter-related results are essential for steps toward achieving the objective:

1. Supportive environment is one in which sustained political commitment and advocacy policy at all levels of health care, and the community encourages and supports the hip ultrasound screening (policy advocacy, capacity-building at all levels of health care service, financial support, etc.)
2. Improving access and availability of hip ultrasound screening and treatment services increase the likelihood that every child receives the services when needed. Adequate human resources, equipment, training, and referrals are critical strategies to improve the access and availability of the services.
3. Service quality means no missed cases due to “4 eye-quality control” services using a web-based HIPSCREEN platform with regular feedback/actions and that parents perceive the services to be of good quality. Strategies and activities include training and qualification system and supervision of facility-based screeners and experts. Also, the establishment of effective surveillance, monitoring, and evaluation systems.
4. Increased public knowledge requires not only awareness of the hip ultrasound screening and early treatment services but also timely follow-up control visits, good compliance of the parents, and effective home care of children with DDH. A critical strategy to achieve the result is to create a high level of awareness of early diagnosis and treatment of DDH, good counseling of parents, and counseling materials development.

Improving access and availability of hip ultrasound screening and preventive treatment services is insufficient to achieve the objectives. Although the clinical part is the most crucial, the program needs to accomplish all four results to have a possibility of success- “to screen every newborn using hip ultrasound and to provide early prevention treatments”. The policy and social environments must be supportive. The services must be of good quality. The parents should be aware of and follow all the instructions (compliances and follow-up control visits). The activities to achieve each result are mutually reinforcing and take place concurrently. Therefore, at the same time, the more one learns about DDH prevention, the more research questions/challenges to best implement it.

Below are some of the “old” research questions/challenges that need the best solutions:

- What is the cause and risk factors for the occurrence of late DDH?
- What is the best way to reach those newborn babies living in remote rural areas?
- What is the best quality control/supervision strategy in low-resource areas?
- What is the most cost-effective 4-eyes-control supervision system?
- What will be the role of private-sector providers?
- What are the best ways to motivate screeners/experts? Financial incentives and motivation?
- What will be the role of new technologies? Is there any new technology to control the compliance of parents?
- Could handheld computers, personal digital assistants, cell phones with still and video camera capabilities, and other mobile technologies have potential applications in hip screening and treatment? These possible functions include job aids, supervision, monitoring, mapping, and more.
- What are the best indicators for hip ultrasound screening programs to stimulate quality measurements across the program, and how to use them for sustainable implementation?

- And the list goes on...

Future simulation studies will be able to use the rich dataset that has resulted from the National Screening Program, the basis of this thesis. For example, the current thesis does not report on treatment compliance and outcomes of DDH, as the focus here is on diagnosis and quality surveillance coverage rates. Future studies on follow-up results and treatment outcomes are crucial. This dataset can also be used to monitor the patients enrolled in our cohort over the following years and collect information on hip development. This will lay the ground for a study on outcomes later in the lives of our participants and the cost-effectiveness of the screening program.

5.4. Conclusion

This thesis demonstrated that a simplified diagnostic and therapeutic framework of hip ultrasound screening for DDH in newborns could be deployed in a developing country, providing high screening, quality surveillance coverage, and an appropriate treatment rate in Mongolia. The Mongolian experience may support further international discussion on universal ultrasound screening using the Graf technique.

The thesis has dramatically expanded the knowledge of the risk factors of DDH. The evidence that traditional swaddling where arms and legs are extended and hips are in extension and adduction position is a significant contributing factor for delayed maturation of the physiologically immature Type 2a hips and development of DDH. Furthermore, the remarkable performance of hip ultrasound achieved by nurses in this thesis supports the feasibility of the practical alternative where suitable hip ultrasound-trained doctors are not available in remote areas in the future.